

Collaboration to use STACK at the universities of Tomsk

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Abstract: Currently, e-learning is one of the modern educational technologies that are used both in full-time and part-time training in one way or another. Modern computer technologies allow you to use animations, videos, and a variety of interactive content, such as STACK. The purpose of this work is to show our experience of combining three universities in Tomsk, Russia, to create, promote and use STACK tasks. STACK is installed as an additional plug-in to MOODLE.

Keywords: Mathematics, engineering education, the STACK assignments, STACK.

1 Introduction

The collaboration of teachers from three major universities in Tomsk (Tomsk State University of Control Systems and Radioelectronics (TUSUR), Tomsk State University (TSU) and Tomsk Polytechnic University (TPU)) began in October 2019. The purpose of this collaboration is to use computer-based learning in higher education. A major obstacle to using STACK in our universities was the difficulty of developing STACK questions. It takes an average of 3 or more hours to create a high quality task. At the same time, experience in teaching mathematics and programming skills are needed for the developer of the STACK task. We realized that to work effectively, we need to combine our efforts to prepare tasks in STACK and use them in different universities in math courses. For this reason, we created a workshop based on TUSUR in 2019.

If initially we saw the goal of our collaboration only in the joint development of the task Bank, at this point we can already identify the following goals of our collaboration:

- Analyzing complex technical details of creating STACK questions.
- Creating a common Bank of tasks the section-by-section of mathematics.
- Development of various methods of teaching mathematics using STACK and exchange of experience.
- Promoting STACK technology among math teachers.
- Presentation of the results of the collaboration participants' activities.

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2 Using STACK in creating questions on differential equations

The first topic that was jointly developed by representatives of three Tomsk universities was 'Differential equations'. To date, 30 tasks on the topic "ODE to first order", 33 assignment on the theme "DE of higher order", and 15 tasks on the topic of systems of differential equations were created. The results of our joint activities in this area are:

- The technical problems of creating questions on differential equations have been resolved.
- The creation of a Bank of tasks on differential equations.
- A common methodology for creating tasks with detailed analysis of solutions and hints is accepted.

The results were reported at the conferences [1, 2, 3].

3 Conclusion

During our workshop, many serious problems related to creating and using STACK tasks were solved. In addition to the tasks on differential equations created under the guidance of V. A. Tomilenko, TPU teachers supplemented the Bank of tasks of TUSUR with tasks on the topic "Indefinite and definite integral", TSU teachers provided technological support and verification of the created tasks. However, there are problems that we still have to solve. These include: distrust of other teachers to the capabilities of the STACK, the uncertainty of realization in STACK of some types of tasks, different teaching methods and curriculum in different institutions, lack of community STACK in Russia and the insufficient number of participants of the collaboration. Therefore, we consider it important to continue our joint work.

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